

Cost and Return Analysis of Jatropha Bio fuel Plantation in Ramanathapuram District

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Introduction

India has developed rapidly during the past decades, reducing the percentage of the population living below the poverty line from 55 per cent in 1973 to 21 percent in the late 1990s. However, 250 million Indians still live in poverty and are dependent on continued development to raise their standard of living. In order to fight poverty and enhance livelihoods in developing countries the supply of food and energy must be secured; the population needs food for sustenance, and access to modern energy sources is necessary in order to achieve both economic growth and sufficient social and public services.

India depends on import of fossil fuels to satisfy energy demand, and with population growth and economic development the demand will continue to increase. Fossil fuels are finite energy resources, and as the amount of new supplies found is decreasing, the resources will eventually be exhausted. Furthermore, the use of fossil fuels has a severe impact on climate change. Increased fossil fuel use thus conflicts with the increasing global pressure to reduce environmental impact and mitigate climate change.

In combination with the increasing global demand for renewable energy forms, the need to secure energy supply in developing countries has created a demand for biomass energy, such as bio fuels. One of the most common biofuel energy systems is production of biodiesel through transesterification of non-petroleum based oils. Biodiesel can be used in unmodified diesel engines, either alone or blended with conventional petro diesels. For developing countries, production of biodiesels could represent not only a way to achieve economic growth by increasing and securing energy supply, but also by creating job opportunities and as a source of income for the farmers involved.

JATROPHA – AN INDIAN SCENARIO: India is one of the largest petroleum consuming and importing countries. India imports about 70% of its petroleum demands. The current yearly consumption of diesel oil in India is approximately 40 million tones constituting about 40% of the total petrol product consumption.

There has been greater awareness on Biodiesel in India in recent times and activities have picked up for its production particularly to boost the rural economy. Under Indian conditions such plants varieties, which are non – edible and which can be grown abundantly in large scale on wastelands, can be considered for biodiesel production. Some of the prominent non- edible oil seed producing plants include jatropha curcas or ratanjyot, pongamia, pinnata or Karanj, calophyllum inaphyllum or nagchampa, heava brasiliensis of rubber seeds, calotropis galantia or ark, euphorbia tirucalli or shet, boswellia Dvalifolota, neem etc.

Significance of the Study

The rapidly rising and volatile prices of crude have sounded alarm signals throughout the world. Even the world’s richest economy, the U.S. is concerned about energy security, and a comprehensive Energy Bill is on the US Administration’s agenda. It promises to strengthen the incentives for energy efficiency and green substitutes for petroleum fuels. The rush for energy is on in the most affluent countries.

A review article in Newsweek, August 8, 2005, highlights the latest significant developments in what it calls ‘green gold’ ‘fuels from the farm’. It points out that ethanol is one of the new bio-fuels, although it has been around for some years in Brazil and the US. China has just constructed the world’s largest fuel ethanol facility at Jublin. Brazil has, of course, been a pioneer and is a leader in the international use and trade of ethanol. Brazil is fast becoming the Saudi Arabia of the ethanol industry. It would be good for India to copy at least some of Brazil’s success in this regard. Jatropha offers a good prospect as its seeds make good Biodiesel.. The production of bio- fuels improves the rural economy which will bring more enthuse more than one billion lives in the area.

Scope of the Study

India has about 75 million hectares of wastelands, which need re-vegetation. Jatropha oilseed is wild growing hard plant well adapted to harsh conditions of soil and climate. Since the revenue of Ramanathapuram District predominantly depends upon agriculture and having large proportionate of waste & dry lands, study about rehabilitation and reclamation of wastelands through cultivation of jatropha bio fuel plantation is the need of the hour.

Statement of the Problem

Economic development in India has led to huge increase in energy demand, which in turn has encouraged development of the Jatropha Cultivation and bio-diesel production systems. The establishment of the Jatropha cultivation and local community based production can lead to income improvement. Establishment and ongoing improvement of a jatropha system secure a sustainable way of life for village farmers and to land that supports them. In order to reduce the dependence of our Indian Economy on imported oil fuels and chemical fertilizers, bio fuel is the need of the hour.

Thus it is clear that wasteland development plays an important role in furthering the process of agronomic development in developing economies. It helps in two ways, namely it provides employment to the people and secondly it increases the pace of capital formation in the country. Recapitalization of wastelands through jatropha cultivation can help in removing unemployment, increase the productivity of the land and strengthen the economy of the nation. Ramanathapuram District is highly drought prone and most backward in development as it has large proportion of

arid and waste lands. The economy of Ramanathapuram District is predominately depending upon agriculture. Hence studying about cultivation of Jatropha bio-fuel plantation and its impacts on the sustainable livelihood of farmers in Ramanathapuram District is essential not only for boosting up the profitability of farmers in Ramanathapuram District but also for the prosperity of our nation.

Objectives of the Study

The following specific objectives have been framed for the present study.

- To analyse the cost and return structure of jatropha bio-fuel plant cultivation by different farm size groups and their break-even point
- To offer suggestions based on the findings of the study for the prospects of jatropha farmers.

Sampling Design

The Present study proposes to cover the jatropha farmers. As census method is not feasible, the researcher has proposed to follow sampling. The sample farmers are selected by following Cluster Sampling Method. The district is divided into seven taluks namely Ramanathapuram, Thiruvadanai, Paramakkudi, Mudukulathur, Kamuthi, Kadaladi and Rameswaram. Each taluk is considered a cluster. The present study selected 540 jatropha farmers of marginal, small and big farmers from all the Taluks. This selection was made on a simple random basis at the rate of 180 jatropha farmers of each category from every taluk.

In this chapter, the cost and returns structure of marginal, small and big farmers producing jatropha are studied in order to understand the differences in jatropha cultivation practices. For this purpose, the collected data have been analysed with reference to cost and returns structure including various cost components used in the study. Agricultural cost studies provide an important part of information and knowledge essential for the formulation and evaluation of economic policies both at micro and macro levels.

Therefore an attempt has been made to analyze the cost, returns of farms producing jatropha among the category of small, medium and large farmers group in Ramanathapuram district. The items of cost of cultivation considered for the present study are labour cost (land preparation), planting of seedlings, cost of farm yard manure, fertilizers, irrigation and weeding/inter-cultivation/harvesting, interest on working capital, rent paid for leased-in-lands, rental value of own land and family labour.

The relationship between the costs incurred and the returns earned from a particular crop is vital to make profitable decisions regarding the operations of the farm. Hence, this study attempts to analyse and compare cost, returns of marginal, small and big farmers cultivating jatropha. The performance of a crop enterprise and its progress can be estimated by finding the relationship between the costs incurred and the returns accrued from the crop production. Various methodological issues arise frequently in the estimation of costs and returns on account of versatility in farms and production structures.

Methodology

The tool applied to evaluate the current situation is cost-benefit analysis (CBA). Data was collected on the cost factors for the cultivation and on the profits from selling the seeds. This data was entered into a MS Excel-sheet to sum up the discounted costs and benefits for every single year up to the fifth year. This data then built the foundation for the calculation of four economic indicators. The net benefit (NB) is calculated as the remaining profit after subtracting all costs that incurred within one period from the value of all products produced within the same period.

Yield: It was measured in terms of the physical quantity of jatropha produced in kilograms. The Gross Income per acre referred to the sum of the value of the main product of jatropha actually harvested per acre and valued at the actual price received by the farmer.

Net Income was obtained by deducting total cost (Cost C1) from the total income.

Cost Components: In the present study, cost has been categorized into Cost A1, B1, B2 and C1. Cost A₁: It consists of all cash and kind expenses (paid out costs) actually incurred by the farmers. It includes (i) value of hired labour, (ii) value of hired bullock, (iii) value of owned bullock labour, (iv) hired machinery charges, (v) value of owned machine labour, (vi) value of seed (both farm produced and purchased), (vii) value of insecticides and pesticides, (viii) value of manure (ix) value of fertilizers, (x) depreciation of implements and farm buildings, (xi) irrigation charges, (xii) land revenue, cess and other taxes, (xiii) interest on working capital and (xiv) miscellaneous expenses.

Cost B₁: It includes Cost A1 plus interest on the value of owned capital assets (excluding land but including livestock and implements). **Cost B2:** It includes Cost B1 plus rental value of owned land and rent paid for the lease-in-land.

Cost C₁: It includes Cost B2 plus imputed value of family labour.

Among these cost components Cost A1, Cost B1, Cost B2 and Cost C1 considered to cover all possible costs. It may be noted that Cost A1 is the actual expenditure incurred in cash and kind (out of pocket expenses) by the grower. Cost B1 includes remuneration for the owned fixed capital assets. Cost B2 is intended to make the cost comparable between self-cultivation holdings and rented holdings. Cost C1 is the business type costs which include actual and imputed costs of family labour and it becomes the comprehensive cost of production.

Average Cost and Returns Structure of Farmers Cultivating Jatropha

	Cost Component	Marginal Farmer		Small Farmer		Big Farmer	
		Amount	%	Amount	%	Amount	%
1	Labour Cost (Land Preparation)	7510.83	26.24	7755.87	26.10	7597.42	26.18
2	Planting of seedlings	8322.16	29.07	8316.82	27.98	8320.27	28.68
3	Farm yard manure	1842.36	6.44	1786.91	6.01	1822.77	6.28
4	Chemical fertilizer	2092.31	7.31	2742.39	9.23	2321.97	8.00
5	Cost of irrigation	1654.45	5.78	1683.09	5.66	1664.58	5.74
6	Weeding/Inter-cultivation/ Harvesting	2032.18	7.10	2692.16	9.06	2265.37	7.81
7	Total (Cost A1)	23454.29	81.94	24977.24	84.04	23992.38	82.69
8	Interest as fixed capital (excluding land cost) land revenue, cess and taxes, depreciation of implements and machinery	1460.87	5.10	1720.73	5.79	1552.69	5.35
9	Total (Cost B1)	24915.16	87.04	26697.97	89.83	25545.07	88.04
10	Rental value of owned land	2386.38	8.34	2301.36	7.74	2356.29	
11	Total (Cost B2)	27301.54	95.38	28999.33	97.57	27901.36	
12	Imputed value of family labour	1322.85	4.62	722.87	2.43	1110.86	
13	Total (Cost C1)	28624.39	100.00	29722.20	100.00	29012.22	
14	Yield per acre in kgs	5121		4781		5001	
15	Gross Returns (Rs.)	40232.76		39371.41		39928.42	
16	Net Returns (Rs.)	11608.37		9649.21		10916.20	

Revenue, Costs, and Profits of Farmers Cultivating Jatropha

Sl. No.	Costs and Revenue Items	Marginal farmers (Rs.)	Small Farmers (Rs.)	Big Farmers (Rs.)
1	Yield Per Acre in Kg	5121	4781	5001
2	Selling Price Per Kg	7.86	8.23	7.98
3	Revenue Per Acre in Rs.	40251	39371	39928
4	Variable Costs Per Acre	24777	25700	25103
5	Variable Costs Per Kg	4.84	5.38	5.02
6	Contribution Per Acre	15474	13671	14825
7	Profit/Volume Ratio	38.44%	34.72	37.13
8	Fixed Costs Per Acre	3847	4022	3909
9	Profit Per Acre(in Rs)	11627	9649	10916
10	Break Even Point (Sales in Rs.)	10007	11583	10528
11	Break Even Point (Yield in Kg)	1273	1407	1319
12	Break Even Point (Price Per Kg)	5.59	6.22	5.80
13	Margin of Safety (in Kg)	3848	3374	3682
14	Margin of Safety (in Rs.)	30244	27788	29401

It is inferred from Table that the marginal farmers cultivating jatropha in Ramanathapuram district produced 5121 kgs. per acre and earned Rs.40,232.76 per acre while their net returns per acre are Rs.11,608.37. The cost analysis reveals that the per acre total cost, that is operational cost of cultivation (Cost A1) for small farmers, worked out to Rs.23,454.29. The cost of planting of seedlings forms the major component of the total cost of production for marginal farmers. Next to planting of seedlings, the amount spent on the labour cost occupied the major portion in the total cost of production. It is followed by cost of fertilizers, weeding/inter-crop cultivation/harvesting, farm yard manure and cost of irrigation. Table also reveals that the percentage cost on variable inputs (Cost A1) to total cost (Cost C1) is 81.94 per cent for marginal farmers.

It is observed from Table that the small farmers produced the yield per acre is 4781 kgs. and they realised Rs.3,9371.41 per acre as gross returns while their net return per acre is Rs.9,649.21. The cost analysis reveals that the per acre total cost, that is operational cost of cultivation (Cost A1) for small farmers, worked out to Rs.24,977.24. The cost of planting of seedlings forms the major component of the total cost of production for small farmers. Next to planting of seedlings, the amount spent on the labour cost occupied the major portion in the total cost of production. It is followed by cost of fertilizers, weeding/inter-crop cultivation/harvesting, farm yard manure and cost of irrigation. Table also reveals that the percentage cost on variable inputs (Cost A1) to total cost (Cost C1) is 84.04 per cent for small farmers.

It is found from Table that the big farmers produced the yield per acre is 50.01 tonnes and they realised Rs.39,928.42 per acre as gross returns while their net return per acre is Rs.10,916.20. The cost analysis reveals that the per acre total cost, that is operational cost of cultivation (Cost A1) for big farmers, worked out to Rs.23,992.38. Table also shows that the percentage cost on variable inputs (Cost A1) to total cost (Cost C1) is 82.69 per cent for big farmers. The cost of planting of seedlings forms the major component of the total cost of production for big farmers which constitute 28.68 per cent. It is followed by the amount spent on labour cost, chemical fertiliser, weeding/inter-cultivation/harvesting, farm yard manure and irrigation which constitutes 26.18 per cent, 8.00 per cent, 7.81 per cent, 6.28 per cent and 5.74 per cent respectively. The rent for land was 8.13 per cent and interest on farm assets, depreciation of implements and machinery involved 5.35 per cent of the total cost.

Revenue, Costs, and Profits of Overall Farmers

Sl. No.	Costs and Revenue Items	Quantity
1	Yield Per Acre in Kg	4968
2	Selling Price Per Kg	8.02
3	Revenue Per Acre in Rs.	39844
4	Variable Costs Per Acre	25193
5	Variable Costs Per Kg	5.07
6	Contribution Per Acre	14651
7	Profit/Volume Ratio	36.77
8	Fixed Costs Per Acre	3926
9	Profit Per Acre(in Rs)	10725
10	Break Even Point (Sales in Rs.)	10677
11	Break Even Point (Yield in Kg)	1331
12	Break Even Point (Price Per Kg)	5.86
13	Margin of Safety (in Kg)	3637
14	Margin of Safety (in Rs.)	29167

It is observed from the table that the overall farmers produced the yield per acre are 4968 kgs. and they realised Rs.39,844 per acre as gross returns while their net return per acre is Rs.10,725. The cost analysis reveals that the variable cost per acre is Rs.25,193, fixed cost is Rs. 3,923 and the total cost is Rs.29,119 for overall farmers. The contribution per acre is Rs. 14,651. The study reveals that the break-even point of sales is Rs. 10,677 and the margin of safety is Rs.29167.

Findings & Suggestions

From the above Analysis, it is clear that our country has good opportunity to produce Bio diesel and save the foreign exchange. Jatropha can help to increase Rural Employment and Income. It will also provide us self-sustainability and help us in alleviation of poverty from rural areas. Jatropha is suitable for cultivable wasteland by which we can retain soil fertility of fallow lands.

Scientific methodology should be developed to achieve economic viability for cultivators (Farmers) by addressing cultivation myths like sustainable yield, water requirement, Input material etc.

The experiments carried over through out the country are few in numbers and varied. Hence may not be enough to reach any substantial conclusion.

The sustained and commercially viable production of oil seeds and diesel, there after in large volume is yet to be tested.

Higher level of research is required for sustained and regular out put from Jatropha plants.

Commercial viability of Jatropha plantation can be attained through proper mix of intercropping with the Jatropha plants.

The behavior of Jatropha plants is varied in different agro climatic Zones as well as regions across the country. Hence it shall be daring to give monotonous verdict in favour of Jatropha. At some places its production was very good but some regions its growth and yield were not satisfactory.

Use of other non-edible oil source shall be experimented for bio diesel production like Pongamia (Karanj), mahua, ber etc,

With effective use of Biotechnology, problems related to seeds, yield and oil content could be addressed.

Fulfilling demand of 5% blending may not be possible in immediate future.

Jatropha cultivation and bio diesel production should be looked upon as a tool for fulfilling Energy need for a village.

Recommendations

Bio diesel has distinct advantages. Initial cost may be higher, but by using of intercropping techniques and other multilevel production technologies will play a critical role in reduction in production cost and making the fuel economically viable. The following points may be considered for its development in India.

Financial help or grants are to be provided to setup processing facility.

Make available latest technology and know-how

Provide subsidy on seed procurement to stabilize the price.

Provide subsidy to farmers for Jatropha cultivation.

Agriculture Dept at State level should be made the nodal agency to implement the schemes as they have the necessary infrastructure down to village. There should be tax free inter state movement of seeds and bio diesel.

Financial Support For Setting Up Of Bio Ethanol And Bio Diesel Production

Stimulating demand for bio fuel by issuing bio fuels directive, setting national targets ensuring sustainable production, conversion and applications.

Promoting R&D extensively for advanced technologies including second generation bio fuels and establishing bio refineries.

Financial incentives for research design and development

Financial support would be provided to use bio fuels up to 100%.

Converting biomass into a more usable source of energy through technologies such as pretreatment, biological processing, and gasification.

Increase crop yields and making other advances in feedstock production.

Increase yield of oilseeds and to increase oil content of the oilseeds.

Indian bio fuel industry to be provided suitable import duty and other tax concessions for importing advanced technologies for processing jatropha.

Provision of Tax incentives: Partial or full exemption of central excise duties on all bio fuels. Energy Taxation Directives and Incentives for bio fuel production, conversion and applications in stationary, portable and transport applications.

Proposed Fiscal and Financial Incentives: The competitiveness of bio diesel depends on the level of duty and taxes imposed by Central and State Governments on such fuels. If the duty imposed on bio diesel were the same as petrol or diesel, bio diesel would be far too expensive for bio diesel to be competitive. To make our country self - reliant and economically independent, concentration on the following aspects is the need of the hour.

Excise duty, VAT and sale tax exemption or reduction would be provided to all bio fuels in pure form as well as blended for up to a certain percentage with a view to lowering the price of the bio fuel at the fuel stations. Vehicles wholly or partially using certain bio fuels would qualify for certain tax reduction benefits.

Liberalized custom / excise duty on technology procurement for production of bio fuels, would be allowed.

Suitable production based tax benefits would be provided.

Bio fuel technology and projects to be allowed 100% foreign equity through automatic approval route to attract Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) to the sector.

Conclusion

In conjunction with rather low yields it must be stated that jatropha cultivation is only profitable under certain conditions and never competitive to the alternative crop sunflower. Under such economical constraints jatropha is unlikely to substantially increase employment and income in rural areas. We have also found that annual costs depend highly on the yield because picking and post harvest processing does contribute much to the total costs. Because jatropha cultivation is labour intensive, high labour costs are a challenge to gain or maintain economic viability.

The leading oil companies in the world are currently looking forward to tap the excellent business opportunity offered by bio diesel. If the developed process is scaled up to commercial levels by more and more oil companies, it could be a major step towards the creation of an eco friendly transportation fuel that is relatively clean combustion and provides farmers with substantial income. The ultimate success of this programme depends on close interaction of all concerned agencies, proper linkages are required to ensure an end to-end approach.

To conclude, in words of Dr. M.S Swaminathan “in building a paradigm of sustainable development, it is necessary to link concepts and procedures at the macro level with field-level practices to arrive at a way of translating a conceptual response into a reality”.